

Knowledge and Practice of Home Gardening Among Residents in Selected Communities of Makurdi North Central-Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Home gardening is a proven system of ensuring food security, raising income for households, and also contributing to environmental sustainability. This community-based study assessed the practice of home gardening among homeowners in Makurdi town. The majority of the respondents were aged 40 and above (64.4%), were predominantly female (80.8%), most were married (76.9%), and all had tertiary education. 88.5% lived in urban areas. The study found that the majority of Makurdi's residents are familiar with home gardening, while the remainder are not. Sources of information on home gardening included family (68.18%), friends (22.7%), and the internet (9.09%). Access to fresh vegetables and fruits (96.2%), saving cost on groceries (76.9%), physical exercise (80.8%), food security (96.2%), mental health (61.5%) and environmental benefits (76.9%) were identified as benefits of home gardening. 76.9% of the respondents owned home gardens. The study concludes that although some challenges exist, home gardening remains a significant practice with multiple benefits. Awareness Campaigns are therefore recommended to be carried out to help residents of Makurdi to see home gardening as a key strategy for achieving household food security.

Keywords: Home gardening, knowledge, practices, challenges, urban farmers, Makurdi

INTRODUCTION

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), a home garden is a “farming system that combines physical, social and economic functions on the area of land around a family home.”¹ A study conducted in Nepal on the role of home gardening in maintaining household food security found that owning a home garden maintained household food security, ensured food availability for most of the seasons, access to food for household members and provided stability in food production.²

Another study to evaluate the role of home gardens in addressing food insecurity in rural communities of the People's Democratic Republic of Lao found that there was a 21% reduction in food insecurity following a 12% rise in the number of home gardens within three years. Also, there was a significant improvement in dietary habits during this period³

A systematic review of the characteristics of home gardens and their contributions to the pillars of food security in Indonesia found a positive impact on food availability, access and utilization.⁴ A study examined

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the role home gardens play in enhancing food security and sustainable livelihoods in Domboshava, Zimbabwe, and it was revealed that home gardens provide home-based employment, reduction of household expenditure on food, increased income generation, women's empowerment, social justice and equity.⁵ In Kenya, a study to assess the influence of home gardening on household food security in Siaya County found a strong positive and significant correlation between household food security and home gardening.⁶ In Nigeria, a study investigated the contributions of home gardening to household food security and income generation. It was discovered that home gardens reduce hunger and malnutrition, provide fresh fruits and vegetables, and generate income for the owners.⁷ Similarly, another study in Kogi- Nigeria investigated the benefits of home gardens among urban households. The study revealed that home gardening improved income generation, stimulated Agri-entrepreneurship and improved household nutrition.⁸

Despite the benefits of home gardening identified in the studies above, its practice still faces challenges worldwide. For instance, in a study on garden access and barriers for low-income community members in Minnesota, United States, it was found that only 31% of the respondents were active gardeners, despite 91% indicating they would like to own a garden.⁹ Additionally, another study in the United States assessed the practice of home gardening and its association with intake of fruits and vegetables, it was revealed that 30% of the respondents owned a home garden in which they grew edible plants.¹⁰

In Thailand, a similar study investigated the association between home gardening and fruit and vegetable intake among non-farmers, found that only 9% of the respondents owned a home garden.¹¹ Another study conducted in South Africa to determine the drivers of home garden growth beyond food security and income among residents of the Eastern Cape Province revealed that only 29% of households owned a home garden.¹² However, in Lubumbashi, Democratic Republic of Congo, a study of perceptions of the residents about home gardening found that 72% of the households

owned a home garden.¹³ In Nigeria, a study to assess home gardening practices and consumption of selected leafy vegetables in Osun State revealed that 41% of the households owned a home garden.¹⁴

In Australia, studies been carried out identified some barriers to the practice of home gardening. These barriers include lack of space, time, knowledge and support.¹⁵ In Chile, studies revealed the barriers to home gardening to include inadequate space and limited knowledge.¹⁶ Similarly, in Ohio United States, availability of space and housing type were identified as factors which limited or enhanced the practice of home gardening.¹⁷

The perceptions and experiences of rural caregivers of under-five children and stakeholders working in agriculture or nutrition in Siaya County, Kenya was studied. In the study, water scarcity, limited financial capital, demanding physical labour, limited land access and control, and inadequate knowledge and technical support were identified as factors influencing the practice of home gardening.¹⁸ In Ghana, a similar study on household perception and adoption of home gardening techniques found that lack of time and space were the main hindrances to home gardening among the respondents.¹⁹ In Nigeria, another study investigated the benefits of home gardening among urban households in Kogi State. It was found that inadequate planting materials and seeds were the main hindrances to home gardening among the respondents.⁸ Another study was carried out in Kaduna where benefits and challenges of home gardening in Igbabi Local Government Area were investigated. Inadequate farm inputs, poor soil fertility, and pests and diseases were identified as some of the hindrances to home gardening.²⁰

Aim and Objectives

This study aims to assess the knowledge and practices of home gardening among residents of selected communities in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State.

The objectives of the study include:

1. To assess the level of awareness of home gardening among residents of the selected communities in

- Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.
2. To identify the major sources of information on home gardening among residents of selected communities in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.
 3. To determine the proportion of residents engaged in home gardening in the selected communities in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.
 4. To identify the challenges facing home gardening among residents of the Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Setting

This was a community-based intervention study with pre- and post-intervention components, conducted over 15 months in Makurdi, the capital of Benue State, Nigeria. The study targeted urban farmers within and around the university community.

Study Population and Sampling

A total of 26 participants were purposively selected with support from community leaders. Eligibility criteria included residency in Makurdi for at least six months, access to land or container space for gardening, and willingness to participate in training and follow-up activities. All participants provided informed consent.

Baseline Assessment

At enrollment, data were collected using a pre-tested questionnaire that had been adopted and adapted to assess knowledge and practices related to home gardening, food safety, and nutrition.

Intervention

Participants received a two-day intensive training designed to enhance their capacity to establish and manage home gardens using organic resources. Training sessions focused on:

1. Practical approaches to home gardening, including site selection, soil management, and crop diversification.
2. Compost production from household kitchen waste.

3. Formulation of organic pesticides from locally available materials.
4. Post-harvest processing and preservation of fruits and vegetables to extend shelf life.

The training combined lectures, demonstrations, and hands-on practice. Home gardens were subsequently established by participants with technical guidance from the research team. To enhance economic benefits, the products generated were showcased in a community exhibition, which also created linkages between participants and local markets.

Follow-Up and Monitoring

Supportive supervision was provided throughout the study period. Members of the research team and extension workers conducted home visits to monitor garden establishment, composting practices, pest control, and produce handling.

Post-Intervention Evaluation

At the end of the intervention, participants were reassessed using the same pretested tool administered at the baseline stage. Outcome measures included changes in knowledge and practices related to home gardening, adoption of organic resource use, and improvements in post-harvest handling techniques. Household dietary diversity and food security status were also evaluated.

Documentation and Dissemination

All activities were systematically documented through attendance registers, field notes, and photographs. Findings were disseminated through community meetings, stakeholder briefings, and a final exhibition, which served as both a learning exchange and a platform for sustaining market linkages.

Data Collection and Analysis

A structured self-administered questionnaire designed by the researchers was used for data collection. It comprised three sections: Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents, Knowledge of home gardening, and their practice of home gardening. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 20 and presented in tables and charts.

RESULTS

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of residents of Makurdi Local Government Area in Benue State (n=26)

Sociodemographic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-24	1	3.8
25-29	2	7.7
30-34	4	15.4
35-39	2	7.7
≥40	17	65.4
Gender		
Male	5	19.2
Female	21	80.8
Marital Status		
Single	4	15.4
Married	20	76.9
Divorced	1	3.8
Widowed	1	3.8
Highest Level of Formal Education		
None	0	0.0
Primary	0	0.0
Secondary	0	0.0
Tertiary	26	100.0
Employment Status		
Student	3	11.5
Unemployed	1	3.8
Private sector	5	19.2
Self-employed	7	26.9
Civil servant	8	30.8
Retired	2	7.7
Residence		
Rural	1	3.8
Sub-urban	2	7.7
Urban	23	88.5

Table 1 shows that the majority of the respondents (65.4%) were at least forty years old, female (80.8%), married (76.9%), and lived in an urban area (88.5%). All respondents had a tertiary level of education (100%), with the majority being civil servants (30.8%), while others were self-employed (26.9%) or employed in the private sector (19.2%).

Figure 1 shows that the majority of residents in Makurdi Local Government Area are familiar with home gardening, while the remainder are not

Figure 1: Residents of Makurdi Local Government Area who have heard of home gardening prior to study (n=23)

Figure 2: Sources of information on home gardening among residents of Makurdi Local Government Area (n=23)

Figure 2 shows that the sources of information on home gardening among residents of Makurdi Local Government Area include family (68.18%), friends (22.73%) and the internet (9.09%).

Figure 3: Benefits of home gardening identified by residents of Makurdi Local Government Area (n=26)

Figure 3 shows that the benefits of home gardening include access to fresh vegetables and fruits (96.2%), saving costs on groceries (76.9%), physical exercise (80.8%), food security (96.2%), mental health benefits (61.5%) and environmental benefits (76.9%).

Figure 4: Residents of Makurdi Local Government Area who own a home garden (n=26)

Figure 4 shows that the majority of the residents of Makurdi Local Government Area owned a home garden (76.9%), while the remainder did not.

Figure 5: Challenges faced by residents of Makurdi Local Government Area in owning a home garden (n=26)

Figure 5 shows that the major challenges faced by residents of Makurdi Local Government Area in owning a home garden include lack of land (50%) and lack of time (40%).

DISCUSSION

In this study, 88% of the respondents have heard of home gardening. The sources of information on home gardening among the respondents include family (68.18%), friends (22.73%) and the internet (9.09%). This finding agrees with study findings in South west Nigeria where family and friends were identified as the major sources of information on home gardening, accounting for 72.7% and 68.5% among male and female respondents, respectively.²³

Also, the benefits of home gardening identified by the respondents in this study include access to fresh vegetables and fruits (96.2%), saving cost on groceries (76.9%), physical exercise (80.8%), food security (96.2%), mental health benefits (61.5%) and environmental benefits (76.9%). These findings are in consonant with the study conducted in Igbabi Local Government Area of Kaduna State the benefits of home gardening were identified to include provision of fresh food items like vegetables (90%), reduction in family food budget (70%), environmental benefits (50%), and better nutrition (95%).²⁰ Similarly, in Congo the study on the perceptions of home gardening by residents of Lubumbashi revealed that 83% of respondents

identified household food security as one of the benefits of home gardening.¹³

In addition, 76.9% of respondents in this study owned a home garden. This finding is similar to those reported by Balasha et al. who found a prevalence of 72%.¹³ It also agrees with the study findings in Nepal where the role of home gardening in maintaining household food security and enhancing rural women's status in Bajitpur and Musharniya villages were studied. The study revealed the prevalence of home gardening to be 78.6% and 68.4%, respectively, in those villages. However, this prevalence is high compared to the findings in Nigeria where the study of home gardening practices and consumption methods of selected leafy vegetables in Ogun State found a prevalence of 41%.² Similarly, the study of home gardening and its association with vegetable and fruit intake in the United States found home gardening practice to be at 30%.¹⁰ These differences may be due to the focus of the latter studies on specific kinds of plants compared to the non-selective focus of the former studies.

The study also found that the challenges faced by residents of Makurdi Local Government Area in owning a home garden include lack of land (50%), lack of time (40%), lack of water (15.4%), and the activities of pests (11.5%). This agrees with Olajide-Taiwo et al. whose study on the challenges of home gardening among communities around the National Horticultural Research Institute headquarters and outstations in Nigeria found the challenges to include inadequate land (87.0%) and damage caused by pests, diseases and animals (81.8%).²⁴ Similarly, Hansen et al. qualitative study on perceptions and experiences among rural caregivers of under-five children and local stakeholders regarding home gardening in Siaya County, Kenya, identified challenges faced by the respondents in owning a home garden, including limited land availability, water scarcity, and pests and diseases.¹⁸

CONCLUSION

The study found that residents of the Makurdi Local Government Area in Benue State have a high awareness of home gardening. The major source of information on

home gardening among the study population is the family. There is a high prevalence of home gardening among the respondents who also demonstrated awareness of the benefits of owning a home garden. However, their practice of home gardening is faced with challenges such as a lack of land and time.

Recommendations

1. The government and other stakeholders in the agriculture and food sector should provide education and training to residents of Makurdi Local Government Area and Benue at large on modern practices that utilize minimal space for home gardening

1. Awareness Campaigns should be carried out to help residents of Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, see home gardening as a key strategy for achieving household food security. Therefore, they should be deliberate about investing time and other resources in growing home gardens.

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REFERENCES

1. Food and Agriculture Organization. Some basic facts about home gardens: <https://www.fao.org/4/y5112e03.htm>
2. Bhandari, S., Yadav, P. K. & Rijal, S. Home garden; an approach for household food security and uplifting the status of rural women: A case study of Saptari, Nepal. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture – Food Science and Technology*, 2021, 9(10):1792-1798: www.agrifoodscience.com
3. Shrestha, S., Maraseni, T. & Apan, A. Enhancing food security through home gardening: A case study in Phoukoud District, Lao PDR. *Agriculture*. 2025: <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture>

4. Saediman, H., Gafaruddin, A., Hidrawati, H., Salam, I., Ulimaz, A., Rianse, I. S., Sarinah, S. & Taridalah, S. A. The contribution of home food gardening program to household food security in Indonesia: A review. *WSEAS Transactions on Environment and Development*, 2021, 17(75).
5. Charachimwe, R. R. & Mangwende, S. The role of home gardens in enhancing food security and sustainable livelihoods. A case study of Domboshava household gardens. *International Journal of Agronomy and Agricultural Research*, 2018, 13(6):24-39. <http://www.innspub.net>
6. Anyona, E. A., Obuoyo, J. & Mutavi, I. Influence of home gardening on household food security in Rarieda Sub-County of Siaya County of Kenya. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, 2024, 8(6). <https://dx.doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2024.806010>
7. Adeoye I. B., Oyedele, O. O., Ngbede, S. O., Amao, I. O., Alabi, O. O., Bamimore, K. M., Oladunjoye, M. T., Owojori, T. O., Kenneth-Obosi, O., Kanu, O., Nwankwo, E., Idris, B. A., Ogundeyi, A., Akinpelu, C. A. & Olajide-Taiwo, L. O. Home garden contributions to household food security and income among Nigerian households. *Nigerian Journal of Horticultural Science*, 2018, 23.
8. Adebayo, S. A., Bolarin, O., Kayode, A. O. & Mathew, T. O. Benefits of home garden farming practices among urban households in Kogi State, Nigeria. *SVU-International Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 2024, 6(1):98-105.
9. Duerst, C. K., Williams, R., Lopez, J. & LaVergne, D. Garden access and barriers for low-income community members. *Journal of Agriculture, Food Systems and Community Development*, 2023, 14(1): 271-284. <https://doi.org/10.5304/jafscd.2024.141.008>
10. Kegler, M. C., Prakash, R., Hermstad, A., Williamson, D., Anderson, K. & Haardorfer, R. Home gardening and associations with fruit and vegetable intake and BMI. *Public Health Nutrition*, 2020, 23(18): 3417-3422. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10200511/>
11. Phulkerd, S., Thapsuwan, S., Gray, R. & Chamrathirong, A. Characterizing urban home gardening and associated factors to shape fruit and vegetable consumption among non-farmers in Thailand. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 2020, 17(15):5400. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343239761>
12. Onomu, A. R., Aliber, M., Taruvinga, A., Chinyamurindi, W. T. & Megbowon, E. T. Drivers of home garden growth beyond food security and income: Lessons from South Africa. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 2022, 11(5):144-156. <https://isdnet.com/ijds-v11n5-01pdf>
13. Balasha, A. M., Murhula, B. B. & Munahua, D. M. Yard farming in the city of Lubumbashi: Residents perceptions of home gardens in their community. *Journal of City and Development*, 2019, 1(1):46-53. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336459457>
14. Ojeleye, A. E., Asafa, R. F., Olaniyi, J. O. & Akanbi, W. B. Assessment of home gardening practices and consumption method of selected leafy vegetables during the lockdown in Osun State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Horticultural Science*, 2021, 26(1). [https://hortson.org.ng/images/journals/2021.Volume/Ojeleye et al 2021 compressed.pdf](https://hortson.org.ng/images/journals/2021.Volume/Ojeleye%20et%20al%202021%20compressed.pdf)
15. Goodfellow, I. & Prahalad, V. Barriers and enablers for private residential urban food gardening: The case of the city of Hobart, Australia. *Cities*, 2022, 126. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0264275122001287>
16. Cerda, C., Guenat, S., Egerer, M. & Fischer, L. K. Home food gardening: Benefits and barriers during the COVID-19 pandemic in Santiago, Chile. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 2022, 6:841386. <https://www.frontiersin.org/>
17. Schupp, J. L., Castellano, R. S., Sharp, J. & Bean,

- M. Exploring barriers to home gardening in Ohio households. *Local Environment*, 2015, 21(6):1-16. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273910462_Exploring_barriers_to_tome_gardenin_in_Ohi_o_households
18. Hansen, L. S., Kihagi, G. W., Agure, E., Muok, E. M., Mank, I., Danquah, I. & Sorgho, I. Sustainable home gardens in Western Kenya: A qualitative study for co-designing nutrition-sensitive interventions. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 2023,103.<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0743016723001985>
 19. Asante, I. S., Aidoo, M., Prah, S., Hagan, M. A. & Sackey, C. W, Achieving food security: Household perception and adoption of home gardening techniques in Ghana. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 2024, 18 . <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666154324003661>
 20. Ijah, A. A., Ishola, B. F., Ayodele, J. T., Danbaki, C. A., Oladele, O. N., Yahaya, U. F., & Olukotun, O. Benefits and challenges of home garden in Rigachikun District of Igbabi Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, 2020, 4 (6) : 12 - 17.<https://rsisiinternational.org/journals/ijriss/Digital-Library/volume-4-issue-6/12-17.pdf>
 21. City Population. Benue . <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/NGA007benue>
 22. Cochran, W. G. Sampling Techniques (3rd ed.). John Wiley and Sons. Wiley.1977
 23. Daudu, A. K. & Abdulwahab, S. A. Sex of household heads and attitudes towards home gardening in Southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 2025,29(1):91-108. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/388555085>
 24. Olajide-Taiwo, F. B., Effi, M. F., Popoola, F. O., Akinkumi, O. Y., Adeniyi, H. A. & Olajide-Taiwo, L. O. Challenges in home garden in communities around National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) stations in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Horticultural Science*, 2018, 23 . <https://hortson.org.ng/images/Journals/2018Volume/OlajideTaiwo2etal2018compressed.pdf>